

**EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF SERONEGATIVE SPONDYLITIS: DIFFICULTIES AND ERRORS
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Early diagnosis of seronegative spondyloarthritis, in the absence of radiological signs, is a problem not only for primary care physicians but even for an experienced specialist in the field of rheumatology, as some infectious diseases, for example, chronic brucellosis may debut with similar clinical manifestations, complicating diagnosis and treatment. This article reports on the clinical case of a patient who was previously diagnosed with early seronegative spondyloarthritis and was treated in accordance with the latest recommendations to no avail. As a result, the patient's condition deteriorated in dynamics. We are analyzing this case to identify the difficulties of diagnosis and the causes of the error that led to the temporary disability of the patient.

Keywords: seronegative spondyloarthritis, chronic brucellosis, early diagnosis.

Introduction: In the last few decades, notions about seronegative spondyloarthritis (SpA) have changed significantly and new diagnostic criteria have appeared (ASAS, 2009 and 2012) based on two main diagnostic criteria: the presence of a genetic marker – HLA B27 and sacroiliitis confirmed by MRI or radiography. But as practice shows, the presence of these criteria did not help clinicians in the early diagnosis of SpA in the endemic brucellosis zone. Early diagnosis and detection of brucellosis in people whose profession is not related to animal husbandry remains a problem. At the same time, a timely diagnosis and adequate therapy, will help to avoid the process of transition to a chronic form and the development of long-term disability and invalidity.

Case: a 46-year-old woman complained of pain and movement restrictions in the cervical spine, the intensity does not depend on the time of day, pain and swelling of the right elbow joint, aching bones and muscles, severe sweating, especially in the palms, anxiety up to panic attacks, menstrual cycle disorders, fatigue. The patient has been ill for 2 years, the onset of the disease with pain and restriction of movement in the right shoulder joint, severe sweating, wave-like fever at night, up to a maximum of 38°C with periods of chills and loss of 5 kg. Several times she received courses of antibacterial therapy with a temporary positive effect. Complete blood count (CBC): leukocytes – $4.42 \times 10^9/l$, platelets – 63 per microliter of blood, hemoglobin – 131 g/l, neutrophils – 22.1%, lymphocytes – 65%, ESR – 19 mm/h; a slight increased liver transaminases: ALT — 142 U/L at a rate of 32 U/L, AST 40 U/L at a rate of 31 U/L.

After 3 months, the patient started complaining to pain and movement restrictions in the cervical spine (CS), thoracic spine (ThS), lumbosacral spine (LSS), pain throughout the circumference of the chest associated with the act of breathing, was treated with topical nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) with a

temporary effect. Further, the pain in the LSS intensified with irradiation to the legs, subfebrile fever persisted. There was a single episode of stomatitis.

Considering fever, stomatitis and progression of articular syndrome, the presence of anemia (hemoglobin decreased to 98 g/l), low platelet level (152 per microliter of blood), high ESR (51 mm/hour), CRP (60 mg/ml) and a history of missed abortion in anamnesis (2017 y.), the patient was examined for systemic connective tissue diseases: ANA – negative, ANCA – negative, anti-CCP – negative, anti-ds DNA – negative, antiphospholipid antibodies – negative, anti-Cardiolipin IgG/IgM – negative, anti- β 2-glycoprotein IgG/IgM – negative. Passed infection tests: ELISA on chlamydia IgG/IgM — negative, ureaplasma IgG/IgM — negative, mycoplasma IgG/IgM — negative, yersiniosis IgG/IgM — negative. Twice the patient was tested for brucellosis in different laboratories: Huddleson's agglutination test – 2+, Wright agglutination test – 1:100, but the results of these tests were ignored. Lymphocytosis in blood tests (48.9-36%) persisted. She passed blood tests for parasitic and fungal infections: *Ascaris lumbricoides* IgG – negative, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, IgG – negative, *Giardiasis* IgG – positive, IgA – doubtful, *Opistorchis* IgG/IgM – negative, *Toxocara* IgG – negative, *Trichinella* IgG – negative, *Echinococcus* IgG – negative. Protein electrophoresis (protein fractions) showed dysproteinemia due to an increase in α 1 (6.3%) and β 2 (6.7%) fractions. The patient underwent an MRI of all parts of the spine: MRI of CS revealed signs of posterocentral herniated intervertebral discs (IVD) at levels C5-C6, C6-C7, IVD protrusion C4-C5. There were not any changes on the MRI of ThS. On MRI of LSS shows signs of IVD protrusion at levels L2-L3, L4-L5, L5-S1. She passed an analysis for genetic typing of the HLA B27 antigen, the result was positive, but no pathology was detected on radiography of the sacroiliac joints. Rheumatologist at the place of residence diagnosed «Seronegative spondyloarthritis» and recommended methylprednisolone 8 mg/day, sulfasalazine

2000 mg/day and celecoxib 120 mg/day with some improvements. Then she was examined by another rheumatologist and diagnosed «Dorsopathy, widespread spondyloarthritis, multiple protrusions of intervertebral discs, vertebrogenic pain syndrome, radicular pain syndrome» and recommended NSAIDs, chondroprotectors and muscle relaxants, with a temporary positive insufficient effect. Due to the insufficient positive effect, the patient was consulted by a rheumatologist at her place of residence and diagnosis was changed to «Ankylosing spondylitis (AS), HLA B27 associated, early stage, peripheral form» and the patient was prescribed anti-cytokine therapy: TNF- α inhibitor – golimumab 50 mg, once monthly. After 6 months of pathogenetic therapy, the patient complained of pain and swelling of the left knee joint, synovitis was detected on ultrasound of the knee joint. Pain in the ThS also progressed, severe sweating and pain in the LSS persisted, but without symptoms of radicular syndrome. The MRI of the ThS was repeated: the picture of osteochondrosis of the ThS. MRI of the LSS revealed circular protrusions of the IVD between L4-L5, L5-S1, as

well as aseptic spondylitis of the L5-S1 bodies (Figure 1), osteoarthritis of the ileosacral articulation (ISA). 1,5 years ago, the patient was consulted by this rheumatologist to clarify the diagnosis and determine the tactics of treatment, as back pain persists, a picture of bursitis in the right elbow joint joined, pronounced sweating persisted. **Epidemiological history:** the patient lived in the village until she was 16 years old, where she consumed homemade milk and cattle meat. This can be considered as a re-infection.

Materials and results: an objective assessment revealed hyperhidrosis of the palms, dermatographism of the skin. Bone and joint system: the act of compressing the brushes is complete, the compression force is not reduced. Pain and swelling of the right elbow joint. Tomayer test is negative, Kushelevsky type I/II/III tests are negative, Forestier's test is negative. Moderate restriction of movement in the cervical spine. Physical examination of internal organs revealed no pathology. respiratory rate 16 per min, heart rate 85 per minute, pulse 85 per minute, blood pressure 110/70 mm.Hg.

Table №1

Laboratory parameters of the patient in dynamics

Parameters	15.02.2021 (before treatment)	06.03.2021 (during treatment)	25.03.2021 (immediately after the 1st course of treatment)	22.05.2021 (before the start of the 2nd course of treatment)
Hemoglobin, г/л	142	131	123	128
Erythrocytes, 10*12	4,41	4,3	4,07	4,32
Platelets, 10*9	356	234	228	241
Leucocytes, 10*9	6,68	7,5	6,48	6,3
Lymphocytes, %	31,8	43,6	43	43,82
ESR, мм/час	52	16	20	14
CRP, мг/л	6,4	2,8	1,5	3,8
RF	negative	negative	negative	negative
HLA B27 (ELISA and immunoblotting)	not detected	-	-	-
determination of antigen-binding lymphocytes of brucellosis specificity	negative	-	-	-
Wright 's Agglutination Reaction	negative	-	negative	-
Reaction Agglutination reaction on glass (Huddleson)	postive	-	negative	-
ELISA brucellosis IgG	positive	-	-	positive
ELISA brucellosis IgM	negative	-	-	positive
ELISA brucellosis IgA	negative	-	-	negative

Repeated analysis for HLA B27 by specific hybridization based on fluorescent amplification and immunoblotting showed a negative result. The patient received anti-cytokine therapy, therefore, before starting antibacterial therapy, she submitted an immunogram before starting therapy and after the end of the 1st course of treatment (Table №2).

Table №2

Immunogram of the patient before and after treatment of brucellosis infection

Parameters	Before treatment	After treatment	Normal range
Immunogram (Humoral immunity IgA,IgM,IgG)			
IgA		2,33	
IgG		9,15	
IgM		0,71	
Immunogram (Cellular Immunity)			
T-lymphocytes (CD3)	52,01	65% (1.934)	52-76% (0.95-1,8)
B-lymphocytes (CD 20)	23,12	20% (0.600)	6-18% (0.15-0,40)
T-lymphocytes T-helpers (CD4)	58,33	29% (0.870)	31-46% (0.57-1,1)
Cytotoxic T-lymphocytes (CD8)	22,12	38% (1.140)	23-40% (0.45-0,85)
Immunoregulatory index (II) (CD 4/CD8)	2,6	0.8	1.2-2.0
Natural killers, NK cells (CD16+56)	21,31	13% (0.390)	9-19% (0.18-0,42)
Conclusion:	Increased B-lymphocytes. And also increased the % of T-helpers who take part in the induction of a specific immune response. II increased due to a decreasing of cytotoxic lymphocytes. The level of NK increased, which are able to lyse target cells infected with viruses and other intracellular agents.	The total number of white blood cells are normal. Absolute lymphocytosis. The relative number of B-lymphocytes is normal. The relative and absolute content of T-cell subpopulations is within the normal range, however, the ratio of CD4-T-helper and CD8 T-cytotoxic is reduced. The relative number of NK cells are normal.	

The aforementioned immunograms demonstrate the conditions of the immune system in dynamics. For example, there was not immune reaction on the immunogram in the beginning of therapy. On a repeated immunogram after 2 months, in the end of the 1st course of combination therapy (fluoroquinolones + recombinant human interleukin-2), we can see positive shifts in the immune response, that is, taking of the

immunomodulator, the immune system rebooted and began to activate as it should in the presence of an infectious agent and shows the height of the immune response to infection. The patient also underwent instrumental study (Table №3) before and after the first therapy, where positive dynamics were observed amid treatment, despite the inadequate immune response during treatment with immunosuppressant.

Table №3

Results of instrumental studies

method of study	Before treatment (15.02.2021r)	After the first course of treatment (22.05.2021)
MRI	MRI of the LSS revealed circular protrusion of discs between L4-L5, L5-S1, as well as aseptic spondylitis of L5-S1 bodies, arthrosis of ileosacral joints. MRI of ileosacral articulation in STIR mode: no data for acute sacroiliitis were found.	MRI LSS – osteochondrosis, moderate degenerative-dystrophic changes of LSS. Protrusion of L4-L5, L5-S1. The MRI picture may correspond to the complications of spondylitis at the L5-S1 level.
Joint ultrasound	Ultrasound of the right elbow joint: signs of chronic bursitis of the olecranon bursa. A small amount of fluid in the humeroulnaris and humeroradialis joints up to 2 ml. Uneven thinning of hyaline cartilage. Osteophytes. Ligamentopathy of medial and collateral ligaments.	Ultrasound of the elbow joints: pathological fluid was not detected. Uneven thinning of hyaline cartilage. Osteophytes.

Notable changes on MRI of the LSS. On the cross-section MRI image of the spine, there are similar signs of Brodie's abscess (sluggish primary chronic intraosseous abscess) in the bodies of the L5-S1 vertebrae, which is regarded as one of the special types of spine osteomyelitis, characteristic, including brucellosis spondylitis (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. MRI of the lumbosacral spine before therapy.

Fig.2. MRI of the lumbosacral spine after therapy

Ultrasound examination of the elbow joints also showed positive dynamics: relief of signs of bursitis and inflammation of the ligaments. The patient underwent X-ray densitometry, where osteopenia was found due to vitamin D deficiency and to patient was prescribed vitamin D at a dose of 3000 units per day.

Based on clinical manifestations (prolonged wave-like subfebrile fever), intoxication (chills, pain in bones and muscles, headaches, decreased appetite), astheno-vegetative syndrome (weight loss, weakness, anxiety, panic attacks), neuromuscular and articular syndromes (polyarthralgia) and symptoms of damage to the autonomic nervous system (instability Blood pressure, palpitations)), laboratory studies (lymphocytosis, positive result of Wright and Huddleson agglutination tests, antigen-binding lymphocytes of brucello-

sis specificity; ELISA for brucellosis with the negativity of the antibody to HLA B27 and the entire spectrum of rheumatological markers), instrumental studies (ultrasound signs of chronic bursitis of the olecranon bursa. Ligamentopathy of medial and collateral ligaments; MRI – picture of osteochondrosis of ThS. Circular protrusion of discs between L4-L5, L5-S1, aseptic spondylitis of vertebra body in L5-S1, osteoarthritis of the ileosacral joints), the presence of risk factors in the epidemiological history (reinfection) is diagnosed: Primary chronic brucellosis, decompensation stage, endogenous reinfection, with focal manifestations: spondyloarthrosis with neuromuscular syndrome, aseptic osteomyelitis of the L5-S1, bursitis of the right elbow joint, ligamentopathy, astheno-vegetative syndrome (sweating, hyperhidrosis of the palms, weakness, anxiety), constitutional manifestations:

wave-like fever, weight loss in debute, gynecological manifestations: miscarriage, dysmenorrhea. Osteopenia. Increased risk of fractures.

Treatment. According to the latest clinical protocol dated 03/29/2021 y., there are standard and alternative etiotropic therapy regimens for various forms of brucellosis. The patient needed several courses of treatment. **The first course of treatment (February-March 2021 y.):** antibacterial therapy: levofloxacin 1000 mg / day for 45 days; immunomodulator: a dosage form of recombinant interleukin-2 people – Roncoleukin 500,000 units 1 ml subcutaneously 1 time every 3 days (72 hour interval), a course of 5 injections under the control of CBC after each injection, **despite the therapy, patient complained to the persistence of pains in the cervical and thoracic spine more in the evening and at rest, tinnitus, instability of blood pressure.** The patient's mood and sleep improved. Due to the incomplete effectiveness of the 1st course of treatment under the control

of immunogram, to the patient was recommended the 2nd course of treatment: norfloxacin 500 mg, 1 tablet 2 times a day for 42 days, and Roncoleukin 500,000 units 1 ml subcutaneously 1 time every 3 days (interval 72 hours) 10 course of administration under the control of CBC per 1 time a week. At the moment, the patient is receiving the 2nd course of treatment, which she tolerates well.

Discussions: This clinical case clearly shows the difficulties of differential diagnosis of early SpA and chronic forms of brucellosis, especially when the patient has primary chronic brucellosis, when there is no acute period of infection with vivid symptoms of intoxication, fever syndrome and clinical manifestations are erased, imitating various other diseases accompanied by articular, neuromuscular, astheno-vegetative syndromes with wave-like fever. Table №4 shows the data on which manifestations this patient had in favor of the SpA diagnosis and which in favor of chronic brucellosis.

Table №4

Comparative table of clinical, laboratory and instrumental features of the patient based on diagnostic criteria of SpA and standard case diagnosis in chronic brucellosis.

Signs of chronic brucellosis according to the standard case diagnosis	Patient Information	ASAS criteria (2009 y.)
Subfebrile undulant fever	+	Not typical
Sweating (night sweats, hyperhidrosis of the extremities)	+	Not typical
Autonomic neuropathy (blood pressure instability, palpitations)	+	Not typical
Intoxication syndrome	+	Not typical
Asthenovegetative syndrome (weight loss, asthenia, feeling of anxiety, feeling of unease, panic attacks)	+	Sometimes losing weight may be
Generalized lymphadenopathy	+	Not typical
Polyarthralgia, polymyalgia, osteodynia	The patient can not localize the pain.	-
Articular syndrome		
Back pain	The pain can be both inflammatory and mechanical	Inflammatory back pain
Sometimes	Morning stiffness up to 30 minutes in the debut	Morning stiffness with a duration of more than 40 minutes
Radicular syndrome	+	Not typical
Bursitis	+	Not typical
Lesion of the ligamentous apparatus (ligamentopathy)	+	Enthesitis, commonly in the peripheral form of SpA
Lesion of the sternocostal articulation	+	Not typical
Unilateral sacroiliitis, sometimes bilateral sacroiliitis is possible, which disappears after treatment	Was not detected in the patient	Bilateral sacroiliitis
There may be spondylosis, spondyloarthrosis, spondylodiscitis, osteochondrosis	Spondylitis, osteochondrosis with multiple protrusions	Spondylitis
Vertebral osteomyelitis	Brodie's abscess	Not typical

Laboratory diagnostics		
Possible positivity by HLA-B27	It was not detected during repeated laboratory testing by different methods	Positivity by HLA-B27
Possible. There is no clear correlation with the activity of the disease with laboratory indicators	Was not detected in the patient	High CRP levels
The positivity of serological analyses, ELISA and ABL of brucellosis specificity to varying degrees	+	Not typical
The epidemiological history of the patient is of great importance	the patient lived in the village when she was a child, where she consumed homemade milk and cattle meat	Not important
Treatment		
Temporary positive effect of taking NSAIDs	The short-term and incomplete effect.	The positive effect from NSAID
A good positive effect on taking fluoroquinolone antibiotics	A positive effect was observed in combination with recombinant interleukin-2 people	Not typical

This patient, as a result of chronic brucellosis, developed a degenerative spinal disease due to a decrease in bone density with limited mobility and severe pain syndrome, which led to temporary disability.

Conclusion. From this clinical case, it is necessary to draw the correct conclusion that it is necessary to increase awareness of chronic brucellosis among doctors, to whom patients usually come with various complaints, most often they are general practitioners, rheumatologists, neuropathologists and others, depending on the predominance of focal symptoms. Otherwise, in patients with late diagnosis, untimely and incomplete treatment, the disease may go into the stage of decompensation with the preservation of residual complications for life.

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